

IS THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON COACHING TECHNOLOGIES A MECHANISM FOR FORMATION AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM?

S.E. Kabulova

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute, "Pedagogy and Psychology" department teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20552623>

Abstract. *In this article, the main task of the current education system is to train specialists who can meet the needs of society, think independently in their professional activities, develop their own capabilities, and have modern views. Therefore, we believe that it is difficult to achieve such a result only through traditional teaching methods. According to the qualification requirements of the bachelor's degree in additional education, the future teacher's professional activity is determined as follows: to carry out pedagogical activities in the status of a teacher of education in general secondary education in accordance with the professional standard of a general secondary school teacher, to carry out pedagogical activities in the status of a teacher of education in general secondary education, to carry out pedagogical activities in the status of a teacher of education in general secondary education. The study of general cultural, professional and subject-specific competencies expressed in the content of the requirements for professional competencies of bachelors in the field of additional education teacher education in this normative document reflects the relevance of using the capabilities of coaching technologies in preparing future teachers for professional activity.*

Keywords: *professional competence, reflexive skills, real time, equality, coaching process, mechanism, innovative, creative.*

INTRODUCTION

As a modern approach in the global education system, wide attention is being paid to the implementation of technologies aimed at improving the professional training of teachers in educational practice. This process involves the development of not only theoretical knowledge and methodological skills of the teacher, but also the formation and systematization of his personal potential, reflexive culture, and collaborative activities.

The conference, organized by various international organizations, including UNESCO's International Institute for Educational Planning and hosted by the Regional Center for Educational Innovation and Technology (INNOTECH) of the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO), brings together educational planning leaders from across the region to create a new collaborative agenda for educational planning and management in the Asia-Pacific region. The regional conference covered the current challenges of educational planning and management in the Asia-Pacific region, as well as the analysis of promising approaches and effective experiences, issues of quality of education, equity and well-being, the impact of governance and digitalization on the education system, the sustainability of the education system in times of crises and climate change, the development of expanded and updated cooperation networks on educational planning for the Asia-Pacific region, the development of new

mechanisms for the exchange of experiences, as well as the strengthening of regional integration processes and the introduction of innovative management practices. This reflects the urgency of improving the content of the application of coaching technologies in the process of preparing future educators for professional activity based on the study of the specifics of their application in the educational process.

In the world education system, the processes of expanding international cooperation within the framework of socio-cultural, humanitarian and scientific research, deepening cultural and socio-ethical relations, forming innovative educational ties and launching scientific projects implemented on the basis of international programs are increasingly expanding. At the same time, the issue of improving the professional training of teachers, increasing their methodological and technological potential through the development of integrative cooperation in such relevant areas as education, healthcare, culture and ecology is of particular importance. In particular, the organization of professional activities based on coaching technologies strengthens the reflexive approach of teachers and serves to develop professional competence. Also, large-scale scientific research is being conducted in higher educational institutions to study professional relations, introduce coaching technologies into the pedagogical process, develop innovative methods and technologies aimed at implementing advanced practices in practice, and strengthen socio-didactic relations between teachers and students on a technological and methodological basis.

In recent years, large-scale reforms have been implemented in our republic to radically improve the quality of the higher education system and bring the educational process into line with international standards. In particular, regulatory, legal and methodological foundations have been created to improve the professional training of future teachers of education, strengthen their theoretical knowledge and practical skills. These reforms are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of education, developing the professional competence of teachers, introducing innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process and forming a flexible approach to the individual needs of students, and are creating the basis for a qualitatively new level of modern pedagogical activity. “Training professional pedagogical personnel who have mastered the methods of education and training, information and communication technologies and foreign languages, and have the skills to use modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process, identifying young people with a high interest in the pedagogical profession and introducing a continuous system of their targeted training and education, improving the quality of education by ensuring the harmony of education, science and production in the field, training competitive personnel, and effectively organizing scientific and innovative activities” were identified as priority tasks. This situation expands the possibilities of clarifying the pedagogical and psychological characteristics and pedagogical conditions of professional development based on coaching technologies in future teachers, and improving the content and model of professional training for students based on the coaching approach.

Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 “On Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026”, No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, No. PQ-289 dated June 21, 2022 “On Measures to Improve the Quality of Pedagogical Education and Further Develop the Activities of Higher Educational Institutions Training Pedagogical Personnel”, No. PQ-2909 dated April 20, 2017 The resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1059

dated December 31, 2019 “On measures to further develop the higher education system”, No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 “On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the country”, No. 422 dated July 6, 2020 “On measures to gradually introduce the subject of “Education” into practice in general secondary educational institutions” and other regulatory legal acts related to this activity serve to ensure the implementation of the tasks set forth in them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The issues of pedagogical technologies, educational technologies, interactive methods, the use of reflexive methods, coaching technologies, coaching, the pedagogical foundations of coaching technologies, the innovative role of coaching technologies, the integration of coaching methods and the formation of a teacher as a professional, professional formation, factors of professional training, pedagogical facilitation in the professional training of future teachers, and mentoring methodologies in the process of higher education have been studied by our scientists S.Abdullaeva, N.Avliyokulov, N.Azizkhodzhayeva, L.Bektursynova, A.Jurayev, M.Jumayeva, D.Karimova, N.Madrahimov, N.Muslimov, N.Norkulova, G.Otaboyeva, U.Rasulov, O'.Tolipov, I.Tursunov, N.Khakimova, M.Khalilova, Q.Yo'ldoshev, O.Yo'ldosheva.

The research of scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries, such as O. Baranova, V. Belikov, G. Chizhakova, U. Graham, Sh. Karimova, M. Klarin, T. Kureneva, N. Nikulina, I. Nosova, M. Rutkovskaya, V. Shagaeva, V. Slastyonin, A. Torbeeva, V. Volodin, etc., covers the professional activities of a teacher, motivational factors of professional training, the role and essence of coaching in education and upbringing, coaching, development of coaching activities as a profession, group psychoanalytic coaching, coaching approach in education, methodological importance of coaching in developing the professional potential of teachers, project activities of a teacher and coaching, coaching as a mechanism for ensuring the innovative activities of a teacher.

Another important aspect of the active application of coaching technologies in the process of preparing future teachers for professional activity is explained by the optimization of the formation of effective communication and empathetic attitudes in learners. That is, the coaching process, based on listening, asking the right questions and active dialogue, guarantees effective communication for future teachers with students, colleagues and parents, helps to understand their emotional needs more deeply. The studies of M. Kraft, D. Blazor, D. Hogan show that teachers trained through coaching use more innovative approaches to teaching compared to traditional methods, which can lead to significant positive changes in student learning.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the training of pedagogical personnel, the main emphasis is often placed on imparting theoretical knowledge and their application in practical activities. However, in real professional activities, it is impossible not to take into account such aspects as independent thinking, decision-making in various personal and professional situations, creative problem solving, the ability to direct one's own professional development, effective communication and cooperation that are required of a teacher. Coaching is an effective collaborative process aimed at revealing a person's hidden potential, achieving personal and professional goals, as well as continuous self-development, which has a positive effect on the formation of not only the necessary knowledge and skills in future teachers, but also such qualities as critical analysis, creative problem solving,

effective communication and personal responsibility. However, there are a number of problems that need to be solved in this promising direction.

As part of our research, we will address the theoretical, practical, and methodological difficulties directly related to the process of preparing future teachers for professional activity based on coaching technologies:

1. Professors and teachers of higher educational institutions operate on the basis of traditional pedagogical methodologies that they have studied, and most of them do not have sufficient knowledge and practical skills in the theoretical foundations, practical methods and techniques of coaching. Coaching is not just a training or lecture, but a process that requires deep professional competence. The need to improve the process of preparing future teachers for professional activity on the basis of coaching technologies is primarily related to the systematic training, retraining and regular improvement of the skills of teaching professors and teachers in coaching. However, today the practice of introducing such programs is limited to professional development and professional retraining courses, which leads to a lack of pedagogical personnel capacity to successfully apply coaching technologies.

2. We can see that the content of coaching technologies in existing curricula is not sufficiently reflected in the content of modules due to gaps in curricula and methodological support. For high-quality training of future teachers on the basis of coaching, it is necessary to integrate special training courses, practice-oriented coaching sessions and situational tasks into the educational process. In this case, the lack of high-quality educational and methodological materials, textbooks, manuals, electronic resources and sets of practical exercises created on the basis of coaching principles is a serious problem.

3. A supportive, open, and developmental learning environment is essential for the coaching approach, and a traditional, authoritarian, and evaluation-oriented environment may conflict with the principles of coaching. In this regard, creating an environment that allows students to think freely, make mistakes, and learn from their mistakes requires a rethinking of the views of most educational institutions and faculty.

4. Preparing future teachers for professional activity based on coaching technologies creates the need to improve the system of assessing students' knowledge. Current assessment systems are mainly aimed at checking how much a student has mastered knowledge. However, personal competencies developed through coaching, such as reflexivity, problem-solving skills, Assessing skills such as initiative through traditional methods is challenging. Therefore, it is appropriate to review the assessment system and introduce mechanisms that are competency-based, track growth, and encourage self-assessment.

5. Future teachers should have sufficient opportunities to apply coaching skills in real pedagogical situations, for example, during internships in schools. That is, the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical skills in pedagogical education raises the possibility that coaching can also be an obstacle to its implementation.

6. The lack of sufficient scientific research on the content of training future teachers for professional activity based on coaching technologies, the lack of textbooks and manuals, etc., make it necessary to scientifically study this problem.

In order to effectively solve these problems, it is important to take a comprehensive approach, improve the coaching skills of teachers working in higher education, implement coaching technologies in the content of educational modules based on modern requirements, that is, create conditions for their wide penetration into the educational audience, and focus on training

innovative, creative, and committed teachers capable of adapting to constantly changing requirements through the introduction of foreign best practices and the full integration of coaching into the pedagogical education system.

In the scientific and research activities of a future teacher of education, it is required to conduct research in the field of pedagogy, to be able to directly apply information on pedagogy and education in practice, to prepare scientific and research works, to have the skills of systematic analysis of scientific data. These tasks require the future specialist to master the competencies related to analytical thinking, independent research, reflexive thinking, social empathy, research of advanced methods and technologies, and the ability to use educational and educational tools on their own. From this point of view, the use of coaching technologies in scientific and research activities, first of all, develops the skills of independent thinking, the ability to see a scientific problem, and the ability to reflexively analyze the process, which are important for scientific research. This will help the future teacher to think based on scientific evidence, to connect theory with practice strengthens their abilities. One of the most important tasks today is to prepare future teachers not only as knowledgeable, but also as spiritually mature, socially responsible and professional individuals. In this process, the integral integration of coaching technologies and spiritual and educational activities is of particular importance.

A unique aspect of the teaching profession is that, in addition to imparting knowledge, it also involves educating individuals. Therefore, it is natural to put forward the requirement that a future teacher should have high spiritual and moral values, patriotism, national pride, and tolerance.

However, despite these advantages, it was found that there are a number of problematic situations associated with the use of coaching technologies in spiritual and educational activities:

However, despite these advantages, a number of problematic situations related to the use of coaching technologies in spiritual and educational activities were identified:

- The coaching process should take into account the interests, values, and goals of each student;
- Coaching technologies are usually aimed at personal development and require new methodologies based on national values;

It is determined that the future teacher of education should be able to develop mechanisms for monitoring and assessing the quality of educational processes in organizational and managerial activities, organize and manage social and spiritual and educational work in a team, make the right decisions in conditions of different opinions, draw up a work plan for the activities being performed, monitor and evaluate the results of the work carried out. Through coaching sessions, the future teacher determines his goals and plans, learns strategic thinking.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Within the framework of our research, the clarification of the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of preparing future teachers for professional activity based on coaching technologies requires an analysis of the content of the concepts of “coaching” and “coaching technologies”. The following is an analysis of these concepts. In our opinion, the reflexive-value component reflects the formation of a system of personal and professional values

of future teachers of education, the ability to analyze their own experience, evaluate their activities, a high level of aspiration for purposeful self-development, and a responsible approach to pedagogical activity. This component also implies planning positive changes through a critical approach to their activities based on coaching, adherence to the principles of national values, humanity, mutual respect, responsibility, and cooperation in educational activities, and the ability to maintain a moral and psychological balance between future teachers and educators.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”
2. Decree No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 “On Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education for 2022-2026”.
3. Decrees No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 “On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”.
4. Decree No. PQ-289 of June 21, 2022 “On measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the activities of higher educational institutions that train pedagogical personnel”.
5. Decree No. PQ-2909 dated April 20, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system".
6. Decree No. PQ-3775 of June 5, 2018 “On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the country”.
7. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 1059 dated December 31, 2019 “On measures to establish the Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education”.
8. Resolution No. 422 of July 6, 2020 "On measures for the gradual introduction of the subject "Education" into practice in general secondary educational institutions."
1. 9.Abdullayeva, S. (2021). Modern pedagogy and educational technologies. TDPU.
9. Avliyokulov N.H. Modern educational technologies. T.: 2001. 69 p.
10. Azizkhodjaeva N.N. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skill.-T.: "Finance", 2003. - 192 p.
11. Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioral Change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191–215.
12. Bennett J., Bennett L. Values-Based Leadership // *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*. - 2004. - Vol. 8, No. 2. – P. 67–76.
13. Block P. *Flawless Consulting: A Guide to Getting Your Expertise Used*. – San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2011. – 320 p.
14. Bloom, BS (Ed.). (1956). *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, Handbook I: The Cognitive Domain*. David McKay.
15. Brockbank, A., & McGill, I. (2007). *Facilitating Learning: A Guide for Tutors, Trainers and Mentors*. Kogan Page Publishers.
16. Brookfield SD *Becoming a Critically Reflective Teacher*. – San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2017. – 304 p.